

Impact of Organic Matter and Humic Acid on Some Growth Parameters of Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.)

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Abstract

This experiment was conducted at Research Station of agriculture college, during the winter season of 2024-2025, to determine the levels of humic acid and organic matter (buffalo manure) in improving crop productivity. The experiment was conducted using split-plots with randomized complete blocks and three replicates. The organic matter additions occupied the main plots, which included three levels (0, 100 and 200 kg ha⁻¹), while the humic addition levels occupied the subplots, which included three levels (8, 12, and 16 L ha⁻¹). The results showed that humic was significantly superior in all traits. The first level outperformed the studied traits, including flag leaf length (32.08 cm), plant height (96.10 cm), and number of tillers (471.7 tillers plant). As for organic matter, there was no effect on most traits, however, the third level yielded the highest average for flag leaf (23.34 cm) and plant height (89.76 cm). As for the interactions, the interaction between the third level of humic and the first level of organic matter outperformed, it recorded the highest averages for traits (flag leaf, plant height, and number of tillers), they reached 34.51 cm, 100.3 cm, and 536.7 tillers, respectively, while the interaction between the second level of humic and the first level of organic matter yielded the highest average spike length, reaching 11.73 cm.

Keywords: *Organic matter, humus, humic acid, soft wheat.*

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Introduction

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.), belongs to the Poaceae family. one of the most important food crops, it ranks first among cereal crops in Iraq and the world in terms of importance, production, and cultivated area (Jabbar & Al-Ziyadi. 2021). It is considered one of the most important small grain crops in the world, because of its strategic role in achieving food security (Al-Ubori & Obaid, 2023). The importance of wheat in human nutrition is due to wheat gluten, which produces the best types of bread (Al-Mugher *et al.*, 2024). It is a source of essential amino acids, protein, vitamins, dietary fiber, minerals, and beneficial chemicals (Shew, 2009).

Wheat production is estimated at 4,248,000 tons for the 2023 winter season, this represents a 53.6% increase over last year's production of 276,000 tons. Nineveh Governorate ranked first in terms of production, with an estimated 773,000 tons, representing 18.2% of the total. Wasit Governorate followed, with an estimated production of 564,000 tons, representing 13.3% (Directorate of Agricultural Statistics, 2023).

Organic matter has an indirect effect on the physical, chemical, and biological properties of soil. It is responsible for every other single factor contributing to the stability of soil aggregates. It also accounts for approximately 50% of the soil's cation exchange capacity. In addition to its impact on soil acidity, its regulatory capacity, and soil fertility, it also supplies plants with nutrients released from organic compounds during their decomposition (Abotlasha *et al.*, 2025). It also provides microorganisms with energy from the building blocks of their bodies. Organic matter also contributes to increased biological activity within the root zone, because it contains some beneficial microorganisms that stimulate biological processes. It is also considered a natural enhancer that plays an important and effective role in improving physical properties (Al-Shater and Al-Qusaibi, 2000; Noqta, 2004; Al-Salman and Al-Gharawi, 2019; Al-Jayashi *et al.*, 2024; AL-Mugher and Al-Hamdawi, 2025).

Fertilizing with humic acid increases the plant's ability to retain water, photosynthesize, and photosynthetic antioxidants. It also leads to increased root length and leaf area index. Humic acid also contains a number of organic compounds, that help increase plant growth, yield, and root system development. It activates some enzymes and inhibits others, increasing plant resistance (Leiby *et al.*, 2025).

It is resistant to harsh environmental conditions such as high temperature and salinity, increases the permeability of cell membranes, and stimulates several vital reactions in the plant (Al-Salmani *et al.*, 2011).

Therefore, the experiment aimed to determine the levels of humic acid and organic matter and their role in improving crop productivity.

Materials and Methods:

A field experiment was conducted at the Research Station of the College of Agriculture, Al-Muthanna University, during the 2024-2025 agricultural season, at a loamy soil texture (Table 1) and was taken to a depth of 30 cm. A composite sample was collected from the field and analyzed in the Soil Laboratory of the Diwaniyah Agriculture Directorate.

Table 1. Some Physical and Chemical Properties of the Soil in the Experimental Field before Planting

Items	Unit	Value
Physical properties	Sand	500.00
	Silt	341.00
	Clay	159.00
Soil texture	loamy soil	
Chemical properties	ECe	4.30
	pH	7.00
	Organic matter	3.20
	Available nitrogen	26.45
	Available phosphorus	17.90
	Available potassium	129.67

The Experiment Included the Study of Two Factors:

The first factor (humic levels) is:

The first level (H1)= 8 L. ha⁻¹

The second level (H2)= 12 L. ha⁻¹

The third level (H3)= 16 L. ha⁻¹

The Second Factor Included Organic Matter Levels, which were:

The first level (T1)= no addition

The second level (T2)= 100 kg ha⁻¹

The third level (T3)= 200 kg ha⁻¹

Experimental Design

The experiment was conducted using a split-plot design with randomized complete blocks and three replicates. The organic matter additions (main-plots) occupied the main plots and included three levels, while the humic acid levels occupied the sub-plots and included three levels. Therefore, the total number of experimental units (3×3) with three replicates= 27 experimental units. Mawaddah wheat variety was used for cultivation.

Field Operations

Soil preparation and soil treatment were carried out prior to planting. The land was cleaned and removed from the remains of the previous crop, and the experimental plot was plowed twice perpendicularly, using a rototiller. After tamping, the soil was left to dry for a period of time. The soil was then smoothed with disc harrows and leveled. The plot was divided into plots according to the design used. Drains were opened, shoulders were created between the plots, and a 50 cm distance was left between the subplots and a 2 m distance between the main plots, to ensure no overlap between levels and experimental units, the area of the experimental unit was (1 m wide ×1 m long). Each experimental unit included five rows, with a planting distance of 20 cm between rows and a planting depth of 4 cm. Planting was carried out in rows.

The experimental plot was fertilized with nitrogen fertilizer at a rate of 180 kg h⁻¹ (46% N), in two batches: the first during the branching stage and the second during the lining stage. Triple superphosphate fertilizer (46% P₂O₅) was added in a single batch before planting (Jadoua, 1995). Potassium sulfate (50% K₂O) was added according to the experimental parameters in a single batch. Planting was scheduled for November 17, 2024. Harvest took place from April 8, 2025, to April 10, 2025, with the two middle rows being harvested.

Traits Studied

Growth traits were calculated at the 75% flowering stage based on field observations:

1. Plant height (cm): Measured using a metric ruler from soil level to the tip of the main branch spike (without a spike) for ten plants randomly selected from the medians of each experimental unit.

2. Flag leaf area (cm²): Flag leaf area was measured using a ruler for ten plants randomly selected from the medians of each experimental unit at the flowering stage, according to the formula:

Flag leaf area= Flag leaf length× width at the widest point× 0.95 (Thomas, 1975).

3. Total number of tillers (m²): The total number of tillers was calculated by harvesting the two medians of the experimental units and converting it to square meters.

4. Spike length (cm): Calculated by selecting ten random tillers from the medians of each experimental unit and calculating the overall average.

Statistical Analysis

Data were collected in an organized manner, tabulated correctly, and then analyzed statistically using the Genestat statistical program. The mean values of the coefficients were compared using the LSD (Least Significant Difference) test at a probability level of 0.05 (Al-Rawi and Khalaf Allah, 2000).

Results and Discussion

Flag Leaf Area (cm²)

The results of the statistical analysis showed significant differences between humic acid and organic matter levels, while there was no significant effect of this trait on the interaction between them.

The results indicated significant differences between humic acid levels in flag leaf area. The first level, 8 L. ha⁻¹, yielded the highest average of 32.08 cm², while the second level, 12 L. ha⁻¹, yielded the lowest average of 14.18 cm². This may be due to the direct effects of humic acid on the plant, either on the cell wall or the cytoplasmic membrane, this leads to increased respiration and photosynthesis rates, and enhanced protein synthesis and hormonal activity, agreed with Al-Basri (2019).

As for organic matter, the third level yielded the highest average, reaching 23.34 cm², while the second level yielded the lowest average, reaching 18.28 cm².

The interaction had no significant effect on this trait.

Table 1. The effect of Humic and Organic Matter Levels, and Their Interaction, on the Area of the Flag Leaf (cm²)

Humic acid	Organic matter			Mean
	T1	T2	T3	
H1	30.31	14	15.22	32.08
H2	31.43	12.79	10.6	14.18
H3	34.51	15.75	19.75	15.19
Mean	19.84	18.28	23.34	
L.S.D _{0.05}	Organic matter	Humic acid	Interaction	
	1.866	3.834	N.S	

Plant Height (cm)

The results of the statistical analysis showed significant differences in the levels of humic acid and organic matter, as well as their interaction.

The results indicated that humic acid levels significantly outperformed plant height. The first level yielded the highest average, 96.10 cm, while the second level yielded the lowest average, 78.36 cm. This may be due to the role of this acid in providing plants with a concentrated dose of essential nutrients from the soil, such as nitrogen, phosphorus, and sulfur, as well as vitamins and micronutrients such as iron, zinc, and copper, which improves plant growth. This is consistent with Al-Basri (2019).

As for organic matter, the third level yielded the highest average, 89.76 cm, while the second level yielded the lowest average, 78.31 cm. This may be due to the availability of nutrients that coincided with the emergence and development of internodes, which created a better incentive for stem growth and development. This contributed to increased photosynthesis efficiency, which was reflected in stem growth and length. This is consistent with what was indicated by Al-Shamari (2011) and Muhammad *et al.* (2015).

As for interaction, it significantly outperformed this trait. The interaction treatment (T1×H3) yielded the highest average, reaching 100.3 cm, while the interaction treatment (T2×H2) yielded the lowest average, reaching 64.47 cm.

Table 2. Effect of Humic Acid Levels, Organic Matter Levels, and the Interaction between Them on Plant Height (cm)

Humic acid	Organic matter			Mean
	T1	T2	T3	
H1	90.27	86.03	80.64	96.10
H2	97.73	64.47	72.73	78.36
H3	100.3	84.57	84.4	79.26
Mean	85.65	78.31	89.76	
L.S.D _{0.05}	Organic matter	Humic acid	Interaction	
	6.206	4.157	7.508	

Number of Tillers (Tillers m²)

The results of the statistical analysis showed significant differences in humic levels, however, organic matter had no significant effect on number of tillers.

As for the interaction, a significant effect was found for this trait.

The results showed that humic levels significantly outperformed the number of tillers, with the first level yielding the highest average of 471.7 tiller m², while the third level recorded the lowest average of 318.3 tiller m².

As for organic matter, there was no significant difference in this trait.

As for the interaction, it significantly outperformed this trait, with the interaction treatment (H3×T1) yielding the highest average of 536.7 tiller plant⁻¹, while the interaction treatment (H2×T3) yielded the lowest average of 310 tiller m².

Table 3. Effect of Humic Levels, Organic Matter Levels, and Their Interaction on the Number of Tillers (Tiller m²)

Humic acid	Organic matter			Mean
	T1	T2	T3	
H1	431.7	368.3	341.7	471.7
H2	446.7	323.3	310	346.0
H3	536.7	346.3	303.3	318.3
Mean	380.6	360.0	395.4	
L.S.D _{0.05}	Organic matter	Humic acid	Interaction	
	N.S	33.81	57.87	

Spike Length (cm)

The results of the statistical analysis showed significant differences in humic levels, however, organic matter had no significant effect on this trait. As for the interaction, a significant difference was found for this trait.

The results indicated that humic levels significantly outperformed spike length. The first level yielded the highest average of 10.38 cm, while the second level yielded the lowest average of 9.33 cm. This can be attributed to increased plant growth stimulation mechanisms, cell permeability, nutrient uptake, and increased spike length. The results of this study were consistent with the results of Radwan *et al.* (2015).

As for organic matter, there was no significant difference in this trait.

As for interaction, it significantly outperformed this trait. The interaction treatment (T1×H2) yielded the highest average of 11.73 cm, while the interaction treatment (T1×H2) yielded the highest average of 11.73 cm. (T2×H2) The lowest average was 7.8 cm.

Table 4. Effect of Humic and Organic Matter Levels and Their Interaction on Spike Length (cm)

Humic acid	Organic matter			Mean
	T1	T2	T3	
H1	9.80	10.47	9.87	10.38
H2	11.73	7.80	9.27	9.33
H3	9.60	9.73	10.1	9.74
Mean	10.04	9.60	9.81	
L.S.D _{0.05}	Organic matter	Humic acid	Interaction	
	N.S	0.727	1.109	

Conclusion

Our study concludes that the use of both humic acid at a concentration of 8 L. ha⁻¹ and buffalo manure at a concentration of 200 kg ha⁻¹ as organic matter improved the growth characteristics, namely plant height, flag leaf area, total number of tillers, and spike length of Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.).

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